

Supplementary Table 2. Results of the normality test as presented in Figure 2 (performed using the Shapiro–Wilk test).

miRNA	Type of sample	<i>S-W</i>	<i>p</i>
hsa miR 145 5p	1	0.82	0.003
hsa miR 145 5p	2	0.88	0.017
hsa miR 29b 3p	1	0.82	0.003
hsa miR 29b 3p	2	0.88	0.017
hsa miR 210 3p	1	0.93	0.170
hsa miR 210 3p	2	0.73	<0.001
hsa miR 193b 3p	1	0.73	<0.001
hsa miR 193b 3p	2	0.81	<0.001
hsa miR 424 5p	1	0.86	0.009
hsa miR 424 5p	2	0.64	<0.001
hsa miR 451a	1	0.98	0.960
hsa miR 451a	2	0.86	0.009
hsa miR 29c 3p	1	0.98	0.960
hsa miR 29c 3p	2	0.86	0.009
hsa miR 195 5p	1	0.93	0.170
hsa miR 195 5p	2	0.84	0.004
hsa miR 146a 5p	1	0.93	0.170
hsa miR 146a 5p	2	0.84	0.004
hsa miR 221 3p	2	0.57	<0.001
hsa miR 222 3p	1	0.97	0.770
hsa miR 19a 3p	1	0.86	0.009
hsa miR 19a 3p	2	0.64	<0.001
hsa miR 128 3p	1	0.92	0.130
hsa miR 128 3p	2	0.93	0.130
hsa miR 200b 3p	1	0.50	<0.001
hsa miR 200b 3p	2	0.41	<0.001

miR – microRNA; miRNAs with higher expression in archival samples (1) than in freshly collected samples (2); *N*- number of observation (Type of sample 1 – N=19, Type of sample 2 – N=20), *S-W*– Shapiro–Wilk test value; *N*- number of observation; *p* – level of statistical significance